

Crowdsourcing the collection and analysis of data on companies' Environmental, Social and Governance performance – WikiRate.org

Richard Mills

*University of Cambridge
rm747@cam.ac.uk*

Abstract

The WikiRate project was funded under the Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation (CAPS) component of the European Commission's FP7 framework - to build an open source, open data, platform and "crowdsource better companies". Research to inform the design of the platform involved surveying the current corporate Environmental Social and Governance (ESG) information landscape to identify ways in which an open approach and peer production ethos could be mobilized to improve this landscape's fertility. The data required to understand companies' impacts is not freely accessible, and in many cases does not exist. This paper describes WikiRate's design, and considers how the project can aid (and be aided by) policy-makers.

Keywords – Sustainability; Corporate Social Responsibility; Peer Production; Crowdsourcing; Open Data

1 Corporate ESG performance data

The primary source of data on a company's ESG performance is their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) or sustainability reporting output. One of the reasons why companies engage in CSR reporting is to improve their reputation (Brammer & Pavelin, 2006), and these reports are in part treated as a public relations exercise, in some cases presenting disinformation or "greenwashing" (Laufer, 2003).

Some companies follow reporting guidelines like the Global Reporting Initiative's G4 – in which case one can expect to find information relevant to a number of standard indicators within their report (e.g. Greenhouse Gas emissions, Environmental Fines incurred) – although for some indicators, disclosure is rare (Corporate Knights Capital, 2014). These reports contain data, that when extracted can be analysed to yield insight into some aspects

of a company's performance. There are however issues with this data.

Many reports are issued without external assurance or auditing of the reported data, and there are questions about the robustness of external assurance procedures (Junior, Best & Cotter, 2014). The G4 standard affords each reporting company room to decide which indicators they will respond to, which aspects of the organization will be included in the scope of the disclosure, and the methods that are used to estimate or calculate impacts. The flexibility of these guidelines limits the degree to which reported data can be used to conduct fair and accurate comparisons.

Companies also respond to requests from some organisations – for example the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) successfully solicits disclosures from thousands of companies every year.

It is possible to buy access to data on corporate ESG performance in an analysable format – Bloomberg terminals offer some ESG data, with access costing around \$24,000 per year¹. There is no open public repository containing this kind of data. There is evidence that some ratings of companies' ESG performance can affect their behaviour (Chatterji & Toffel, 2010; Sharkey & Bromley, 2014) – but these ratings are also proprietary and inaccessible to the public, both in terms of the details of how they are constructed and how individual companies perform.

Insight into companies' ESG performance (through data and analyses) is a commodity around which a new industry has emerged. Investors and companies pay analysts to commission research into the ESG performance of prospective investments or rivals – some research organisations in turn pay for access to machine-readable

¹ <http://qz.com/84961/this-is-how-much-a-bloomberg-terminal-costs/>

data. The public at large are excluded from these ways of knowing about a company's ESG performance.

There is some processed information about companies' ESG performance freely available to the public, and this tends to come from non-profit organisations that research and/or rate companies. Typically the primary output of this activity is a published report that is used as the basis for an advocacy campaign. In some cases data is collected in line with bespoke indicators, and that data and methodology are openly shared². The manner in which this data is collected and shared lacks the standardisation which would allow one to combine data from multiple sources. The way this data is distributed across multiple sites limits its accessibility, and likely also its potential for impact.

2 WikiRate.org

WikiRate has been designed as an intervention in this space, to:

1. Establish an open public repository of data about companies' ESG performance.
2. Bring together data from existing structured sources in one place, in a standardised format.
3. Produce new data by dissecting the reporting output of companies.
4. Provide a set of tools that can be used to analyse, interpret and critique this data in a transparent and open way.
5. Foster a community that understands the available data and its limitations, and which strives to formulate better questions to ask of companies.
6. Push for more and better disclosures by companies in line with the questions that we collectively deem to be important.

2.1 Researched Metrics

Data is being requested, scraped or mined from existing structured public sources, and housed in standard metric containers on the WikiRate platform. WikiRate's "researched metrics" have been designed as a means of asking the same question of a large number of companies and storing the answers to those questions on an annual basis. Each value (or data-point) for a metric relates to a company and incorporates the answer to the question, the year the value relates to and the source of the information. The design of each metric specifies whether it will hold categorical, numerical, monetary or free text data.

Each value also has its own discussion space, for describing where the value can be found within the source

or how it was produced, details of the methodology and/or scope underlying the value where this is reported, and other observations/criticisms related to the value.

Data to populate these metrics can be imported directly from existing structured sources. Volunteers can also conduct their own research to populate metrics with data, by following a metric's "methodology" to find the right value for a company. A microtasking-like interface has been created to facilitate a volunteer extracting data from a company's reporting output. This interface is constructed on-the-fly when a company and a set of metrics are specified. One side of the screen is used for displaying the source, the other displays the metric or set of metrics being researched. Project pages serve as a way of structuring and coordinating research on the platform – they specify a set of metrics and a set of companies to be covered, allowing a researcher to click through to the page for a company that displays all of the metrics alongside the relevant sources.

Driving public engagement on the platform is a key challenge for the project. One proposition being evaluated is that actors who want data can set up projects to collect that data on WikiRate, then recruit people to participate in their project through their existing networks. A pilot project of this type is underway with Amnesty International³. This project focuses on Conflict Minerals Reports that electronics companies are required to file with the United States Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) – it incorporates 16 metrics, each asking a question about how the company is behaving or reporting. Further pilots with non-profit and academic partners are in the preparatory stages.

Microtasking and crowdsourced data collection are no longer novel approaches, platforms like Zooniverse (Simpson, Page & De Roure, 2014) are now well established as a means of recruiting volunteers to process source material. This approach has however not been applied at scale to the collection of data on companies' ESG performance. The WikiRate project aims to do exactly that, and also to engage users more deeply in the research process. WikiRate.org is designed to facilitate both the collection and consumption of data, newly added data-points are immediately available to all as part of the site's public information resource.

2.2 Peer Produced Analysis

² For example *Ranking Digital Rights* and Oxfam's *Behind the Brands*

³ http://www.wikirate.org/Investigating_Mineral_Sourcing_Practices

WikiRate departs from existing crowdsourcing and microtasking platforms by inviting community members to also participate in the analysis and interpretation of data on the platform. Every user has the same range of possible actions (e.g. creating a metric, collecting data, setting up a project, designing a rating) and all of this activity occurs in the open – the platform is designed as an infrastructure for Peer Production (Benkler, 2006).

To pursue the project’s ultimate goal of using the platform as a tool to improve the behavior of companies, it is important that not only the data but also its interpretation and analysis are made freely available in a transparent way. Existing proprietary ratings that have the power to nudge corporate behavior (Sharkey & Bromley, 2014) are opaque with regard to showing how an organization’s rating is derived from the data. Our position is that the power of such ratings can be increased by clearly showing why each company has received a certain score or judgment, and by making this process accessible to all stakeholders.

If encouraging companies to compete on metrics of ESG performance is a mechanism that can be used to make progress on pressing social and environmental concerns – decisions about what questions are asked, and how much all of these *count* in the scoring algorithms, will hold political power. For this reason, one of the central aims of the WikiRate project has been to foster an open collaborative approach to analysis and interpretation of this data - not merely the data itself or a fixed interpretation of what that data means.

A system of “**calculated metrics**” is in development which will allow users to create and share analyses of the data held in “researched metrics”. “Formula metrics” will allow for a wide range of mathematical operations to be performed on sets of metric data. “Score Metrics” will map the values held in other metrics unto a 0-10 scale according to the designer’s position on how those values should be interpreted. “WikiRatings” will allow users to design ratings that produce a weighted average of Score metrics.

The designs of **Score metrics** and **WikiRatings** are based loosely on the methodologies of existing publicly accessible ratings. These award points based on the company’s value for each indicator and then use those points to calculate overall scores and sub-scores. Existing ratings tend to award points on varying ranges, an important indicator might be scored as 0-15 while an indicator perceived as less important might be scored on a

0-5 range. The lack of a standardized scoring methodology limits the extent to which aspects of different ratings can be combined. WikiRate intends to increase the interoperability of rating components by promoting 0-10 scores as the default range – with the relative importance of metrics being reflected through their weights in a WikiRating.

The second aim with the design of WikiRatings is to present their workings transparently. When a user selects a company’s score on a WikiRating they are presented with a breakdown of every metric included in that WikiRating along with the value the company received, how this was scored, and how each score contributed to the overall WikiRating score. Understanding how one WikiRating works should easily be extended to understanding of how every WikiRating works.

The third aim with the design of WikiRatings and Score metrics is to make the act of rating companies accessible. Services like CSRhub and Ethical Consumer⁴ allow subscribers to specify how much they care about a set of issues or themes and tailor the scores of companies accordingly. WikiRate aims to make it possible for users to create their own customized company ratings by using any combination of existing Scores and WikiRatings, or working directly from researched metrics and scoring these themselves. We want all of this activity to happen in the open, where the construction of a WikiRating can spark discussion about its inputs or how these are used, and contributors can borrow or learn from each other’s work.

Formula metrics by contrast are designed with an emphasis on power rather than accessibility. Formula metrics utilize Wolfram Language⁵ as their foundation, and should allow for a wide variety of mathematical operations to be performed on metric data. It should be possible to reproduce the scoring methodology of any existing rating through a set of Formula metrics. Once these have been created, additional companies can be automatically rated on the same criteria if the required input data is added to the platform.

One test case for WikiRate’s calculated metrics system is a live implementation of the *Center for Sustainable Organizations’* (CSO) context-based carbon metric for

⁴ <http://www.csrhub.com> and <http://www.ethicalconsumer.org>

⁵ <https://www.wolfram.com/language/>

businesses⁶. This metric contextualizes a company's carbon emissions by calculating their "fair share" of global emissions based on their economic output, and then comparing this to their historical emissions to produce a number that reflects whether the company's emissions are higher or lower than their fair share. Although the number of companies that produce CSR reports is increasing year-on-year, the proportion of these reports that frame a company's impacts in relation to earth's finite natural resources is not (Bjørn et al., 2016). Enabling context-based analysis (McElroy & Baue, 2013), or the benchmarking of company performance against science-based targets, is a specific use-case that Formula metrics are being developed to serve.

WikiRate aims to provide a platform where methods of analysis that exist as guidelines or spreadsheets (e.g. McElroy & Thomas, 2015) can be developed alongside real data, open to feedback from the community, and used to publicly assess the performance of companies.

2.3 Navigating the metric commons

The decision to allow any user to create their own researched or calculated metrics has the result that many metrics will be created on the platform. This necessitates a means of navigating metrics and sorting the important from the irrelevant or poorly designed.

A voting/preference system has been built into the platform to serve a number of roles. The first of these is to allow users to choose a set of metrics that are important to them. These metrics follow the user around the site such that they form the default lens through which the user views company performance. These expressed preferences also double as votes and are aggregated to determine how visibly each metric will be displayed to a user who hasn't specified their own preferences.

This voting is also central to a feature which is yet to be implemented, provisionally titled the WikiRate Index of Transparency (WRIT). WRIT will prominently award each company a score based on whether they have disclosed the answers to questions asked by researched metrics. The weight with which researched metrics affect WRIT will be determined by how heavily they are used in the system. A researched metric that is used in many popular calculated

metrics will have a greater weighting – and therefore a company would gain more WRIT points by disclosing this information. WRIT can be described as an attempt to gamify disclosure for companies, with the WikiRate community collectively deciding which pieces of information are most sought. Stakeholder demand is one of the determinants of what companies disclose (Fernandez-Feijoo, Romero & Ruiz, 2015). WikiRate aims to produce clear signals to companies about what they should report, and to grow the audience for this information and the level of scrutiny it is subjected to.

2.4 Resistance to manipulation and bias

The nature of WikiRate's subject is such that should the platform gain widespread visibility it is likely to be the target of efforts at manipulating the resource. The overarching answer to this concern is transparency, every piece of content on the site is presented with an edit history that shows which users created and edited it.

Metric values must cite public sources. Checking that a value accurately represents its source is a distinct user action. Where a value is discovered to be inaccurate users are encouraged to edit it, if the value is accurate a button can be pressed that marks the value as having been checked by that user. Company representatives will be encouraged to add data about their company on the site directly – but must declare that they are acting as a company representative.

On WikiRate transparency extends to user voting, which is a matter of public record. This represents a departure from how up-down voting is usually deployed, and is likely to influence the manner in which people vote. It is hypothesized that by making votes public and having these affect users' browsing experience, users will take more care with their votes and these will have a less disposable quality than on sites like reddit.

There are also concerns about bias among volunteer researchers in relation to assessing a company's performance. It is important to establish strong community norms around collecting data by applying a metric's methodology dispassionately to the appropriate source. The distinction between researched and calculated metrics can help to facilitate this. Score metrics and WikiRatings offer their creators free reign to use the data held in researched metrics to rate companies according to their

⁶<http://www.sustainableorganizations.org/context-based-metrics-in-public-domain.html>

own views. For the results of these ratings to be valid the data they utilise must be accurate.

3 Policy for Data

Recent years have seen the introduction of legislation that makes reporting on certain aspects of ESG performance mandatory. The Dodd-Frank Act⁷ requires companies that file with the Security and Exchange Commission (SEC) and are involved in the manufacturing of electronics, to submit Conflict Minerals Reports that describe their due diligence to ensure that their sourcing of certain minerals does not fund armed groups in the DRC area.

The UK's Modern Slavery Act 2015⁸ requires companies that trade in the UK with turnover of £36 million or greater to publish an annual slavery and human trafficking statement describing the steps they have taken to ensure that slavery and human trafficking does not occur within their own business or their supply chain. The European Commission is moving to make "non-financial" reporting mandatory for companies with more than 500 employees⁹

These examples are welcome developments that begin to shift aspects of ESG performance away from self-regulation and towards a legal requirement of greater transparency and action. The UK and EU examples have come into effect recently (or are due to come into effect soon), and they are quite loosely worded, so it is not yet clear exactly what the outcomes will be. One hopes that the result will be a levelling of the playing field in relation to CSR reporting. A major issue with research on corporate sustainability at present is high variance in what companies report on. Some companies disclose responses to many standard indicators, others disclose very little or fail to report on their ESG performance at all. While the choice of whether/what to report is left to companies themselves, those that perform poorly have little incentive to report.

The SEC have recently held a public consultation on revising the content and format of required reporting¹⁰. There is growing evidence of a link between ESG performance and financial performance (Friede, Busch & Bassen, 2015), and many investors now pay attention to ESG performance when making investment decisions¹¹. It

⁷ <https://www.sec.gov/News/Article/Detail/Article/1365171562058>

⁸ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2015/30/contents/enacted>

⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/finance/company-reporting/non-financial-reporting/index_en.htm#news

¹⁰ <https://www.sec.gov/news/pressrelease/2016-70.html>

¹¹ <http://sloanreview.mit.edu/projects/investing-for-a-sustainable-future/>

therefore seems likely that the SEC will move to mandate reporting on certain aspects of ESG performance.

From WikiRate's perspective, increased requirements for ESG reporting, and increased standardization of what must be reported, are both positive developments that should increase the scope of what the public can know about the ESG performance of a company.

The adoption of machine-readable formats for ESG reporting would significantly increase the public's capacity to access and use this information. Reporting of financial data in XBRL (eXtensible Business Reporting Language – a variant of XML) format is now mandatory for SEC filings and for certain filings in a range of other jurisdictions (Markelevich, Shaw & Weihs, 2015), and has been shown to reduce information asymmetry in the Korean stock market (Yoon, Zo & Ciganek, 2011). As part of the WikiRate project scripts have been written that extract financial data from XBRL reports filed with the SEC, for import on the WikiRate platform.

The Global Reporting Initiative have developed an XBRL taxonomy which allows for machine-readable reporting on ESG performance, but only a few examples of reports in this format can be found¹². Widespread adoption of a machine-readable format for ESG reporting would greatly facilitate the production of an open repository of ESG data like WikiRate. At present human labour is required to extract data from CSR reports, with the result that employing people to extract data and then charging for access to the data is a viable business model. This approach has the result that only certain actors can access the data, and a wide range of stakeholders are excluded. From WikiRate's perspective, ready availability of machine-readable ESG data would reduce the burden on the WikiRate community to collect such data, leaving more capacity for analysis and critique of the data.

4 Data for Policy

There are two broad ways in which the WikiRate project and its data may be relevant to policy-makers.

The WikiRate platform and the data it contains may be useful to policy-makers concerned with corporate ESG performance. One assumes that policy-makers sit within

¹² https://www.globalreporting.org/services/Analysis/XBRL_Reports/Pages/default.aspx

organisations that have access to proprietary ESG data through services like the Bloomberg terminal – and so part of WikiRate’s offering may be redundant for this audience. However, even at this early stage WikiRate has a greater breadth of available metrics as compared to Bloomberg’s ESG data, particularly with regard to Social indicators. Where WikiRate is still lacking is in the number of companies covered on these metrics. As of August 2016 over 100 metrics have been created in line with the GRI’s G4 standard, with the number of companies covered on these metrics ranging from 0 to 230. This data-set will continue to grow at a rate commensurate with the level of community activity expended researching these metrics.

As noted in section 1, there are issues with using the data reported by companies to conduct comparisons. The scope, methodology and level of assurance for each data-point should be considered when using this data to assess a company or industry. Unpicking exactly what a company’s reported data means is a challenging task. It is not clear how well proprietary data-providers deal with these challenges and issues with the data may be obfuscated rather than resolved. This is another area where WikiRate’s approach of making each step and aspect of the research transparent and open for discussion could be fruitful.

WikiRate’s WRIT score and the calculation of metric importance could in future potentially be useful to policy-makers in establishing more detailed requirements for nonfinancial reporting. The same mechanism used to gamify disclosure for companies (WRIT) could also supply policy-makers with a list of metrics ordered by their importance to the WikiRate community, along with examples of how they are being used in analysis.

The second way that the WikiRate project is relevant to the topic of Data for Policy is as an exploration of public engagement with data and analysis. Early signs are that volunteer engagement with the collection of this data offers an interesting learning experience to those volunteers. WikiRate is attempting to instigate a large-scale collective research project on the subject of corporate ESG performance. Although the WikiRate platform has been tailored for this subject, there is no reason that the same general approach could not be applied to other subjects where information is available but lacking structure.

The challenge for WikiRate now is to grow a community that can collect and make sense of this data, and further

develop the available tools in line with the needs of this community.

Acknowledgements

This work is supported by the WikiRate FP7 project, partially funded by the EC under contract number 609897.

References

- Benkler, Y., 2006. *The Wealth of Networks: How Social Production Transforms Markets and Freedom*. Yale University Press.
- Bjørn, A., Bey, N., Georg, S., Røpke, I., Hauschild, M.Z., 2016. Is Earth recognized as a finite system in corporate responsibility reporting? *Journal of Cleaner Production*.
- Brammer, S.J., Pavelin, S., 2006. Corporate reputation and social performance: The importance of fit. *Journal of Management Studies* 43, 435–455.
- Corporate Knights Capital, 2014. *Measuring Sustainability Disclosure: Ranking the World’s Stock Exchanges*. Found in: <http://www.corporateknights.com/wp>.
- Chatterji, A.K., Toffel, M.W., 2010. How firms respond to being rated. *Strategic Management Journal* 31, 917–945.
- Fernandez-Feijoo, B., Romero, S., Ruiz, S., 2014. Effect of stakeholders’ pressure on transparency of sustainability reports within the GRI framework. *Journal of Business Ethics* 122, 53–63.
- Friede, G., Busch, T., Bassen, A., 2015. ESG and financial performance: aggregated evidence from more than 2000 empirical studies. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment* 5, 210–233.
- Junior, R.M., Best, P.J., Cotter, J., 2014. Sustainability reporting and assurance: a historical analysis on a world-wide phenomenon. *Journal of Business Ethics* 120, 1–11.
- Laufer, W.S., 2003. Social accountability and corporate greenwashing. *Journal of business ethics* 43, 253–261.
- Markelevich, A., Shaw, L., Weihs, H., 2015. The Israeli XBRL Adoption Experience. *Accounting Perspectives* 14, 117–133.
- McElroy, M.W., Baue, B., 2013. Research needs and opportunities in Context-Based Sustainability. *Financial reporting*.
- McElroy, M.W., Thomas, M.P., 2015. The MultiCapital Scorecard. *Sustainability Accounting, Management and Policy Journal* 6, 425–438.
- Sharkey, A.J., Bromley, P., 2014. Can ratings have indirect effects? Evidence from the organizational response to peers’ environmental ratings. *American Sociological Review* 3122414559043.
- Simpson, R., Page, K.R., De Roure, D., 2014. Zooniverse: observing the world’s largest citizen science platform, in: *Proceedings of the 23rd International Conference on World Wide Web*. ACM, pp. 1049–1054.
- Yoon, H., Zo, H., Ciganek, A.P., 2011. Does XBRL adoption reduce information asymmetry? *Journal of Business Research* 64, 157–163.